

1 Biotrickling filter modeling for styrene abatement. Part 1:
2 Model development, calibration and validation on an
3 industrial scale

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16

17 **Abstract**

18 A three-phase dynamic mathematical model based on mass balances describing the
19 main processes in biotrickling filtration: convection, mass transfer, diffusion, and
20 biodegradation was calibrated and validated for the simulation of an industrial styrene-
21 degrading biotrickling filter. The model considered the key features of the industrial
22 operation of biotrickling filters: variable conditions of loading and intermittent
23 irrigation. These features were included in the model switching from the mathematical
24 description of periods with and without irrigation. Model equations were based on the
25 mass balances describing the main processes in biotrickling filtration: convection, mass
26 transfer, diffusion, and biodegradation. The model was calibrated with steady-state data
27 from a laboratory biotrickling filter treating inlet loads at 13–74 g C m⁻³ h⁻¹ and at
28 empty bed residence time of 30–15 s. The model predicted the dynamic emission in the
29 outlet of the biotrickling filter, simulating the small peaks of concentration occurring
30 during irrigation. The validation of the model was performed using data from a pilot on-
31 site biotrickling filter treating styrene installed in a fiber-reinforced facility. The model
32 predicted the performance of the biotrickling filter working under high-oscillating
33 emissions at an inlet load in a range of 5–23 g C m⁻³ h⁻¹ and at an empty bed residence
34 time of 31 s for more than 50 days, with a goodness of fit of 0.84.

35

36 **Keywords:** Biological air treatment; Biotrickling filter; Mathematical modeling;
37 Styrene; Pilot unit; Volatile organic compound

38

39 **1. Introduction**

40 Styrene is one of the most widely used organic compounds because of its application as
41 an intermediate product in industries that produce synthesized polymers and
42 copolymers, such as polystyrene. Nevertheless, as a consequence of its physical
43 properties (vapor pressure of 0.667 kPa at 20 °C), it is classified as a volatile organic
44 compound (VOC), and thus its emissions to the atmosphere are strictly regulated
45 (European Union, 2010). Styrene photochemical ozone creation was estimated at 14.2
46 (Derwent et al., 1998), and it was identified as reasonably anticipated to be a human
47 carcinogen (National Toxicology Program (NTP), 2016). Therefore, companies should
48 prioritize treating derivative styrene air emissions. Several efforts have been made to
49 report styrene abatement. Traditionally, styrene air emissions are controlled by using a
50 regenerative thermal or catalytic oxidizer. However, the treatment of styrene emissions
51 using bioprocesses has been gaining attention from researchers in the last two decades
52 (Lim et al., 2005; Lu, 2001; Pérez et al., 2015). In particular, biotrickling filtration
53 technology has been demonstrated as a suitable alternative treating the air emissions of
54 styrene (Pérez et al., 2015; Sempere et al., 2011) and to be feasible to replace
55 conventional technologies. Moreover, biotrickling filters (BTFs) are cost-effective. The
56 direct cost (excluding capital recovery) of treating styrene air emissions has been
57 reported to be more than three times lower than that of regenerative catalytic oxidization
58 combined with a zeolite pre-concentrator (Álvarez-Hornos et al., 2017).

59 Industrial air emissions of any facility are characterized by fluctuating conditions of
60 inlet concentrations and gas flow rates related to the random variations in the
61 manufacturing processes and short off closures during weekends. Therefore, industrial
62 BTFs can exhibit a different performance than that observed at the laboratory, and the
63 influence of these dynamic variations on BTFs is one of the current issues of interest.

64 Only a few studies on the pilot-industrial scale (Álvarez-Hornos et al., 2017; Webster et
65 al., 1999) are available, thus making it difficult to achieve a real consolidation of the
66 bioprocess in the industrial field. One of the earlier studies on the pilot/full-scale BTF
67 reactor applied to styrene treatment was conducted in 1999 by Webster et al. (1999),
68 and it assessed several operational problems. In their study, the pilot BTF treated inlet
69 concentrations up to 0.8 g m^{-3} (empty bed residence time (EBRT) of 86 s) with an
70 elimination capacity (EC) of $24 \text{ g m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ and 70–85 % removal efficiency (RE).
71 However, the authors encountered that transient conditions led to unstable biofilm as
72 well as biological and mass transfer limitations. More recently, Álvarez-Hornos et al.
73 (2017) demonstrated the feasibility of a BTF to treat styrene air emissions from a fiber-
74 reinforced plastic industry with a maximum EC of $18.8 \text{ g m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ (an RE of 75.6%, an
75 EBRT of 31 s, and an inlet concentration of 0.21 g m^{-3}). Note that this application was
76 performed under conditions of intermittent irrigation, which is the common operational
77 protocol in the industry (Álvarez-Hornos et al., 2017; Deshusses and Webster, 2000;
78 Lafita et al., 2012). Intermittent recycling water has been demonstrated as an
79 advantageous operation strategy in terms of economic savings associated with energy
80 costs and processes (Deshusses and Webster, 2000; Sempere et al., 2008).
81 Researchers in the field agree that mathematical modeling is useful to improve the
82 knowledge about bioprocesses, to understand the effect of the variations of the
83 operational parameters, and to predict the overall performance of the system, thus
84 avoiding the excessive consumption of time and resources (Alonso et al., 1998; Okkerse
85 et al., 1999; Zarook et al., 1997). Traditionally, phenomenological models have been
86 used to simulate biofilters (Álvarez-Hornos et al., 2009; Das et al., 2011), BTFs (Kim
87 and Deshusses, 2003), and trickled bed biofilters (Liao et al., 2008). These
88 configurations are usually described by steps in a series (gas–liquid–biofilm) based on

89 the mass balances including the main mechanisms, such as diffusion, mass transfer, and
90 kinetics (Devinny and Ramesh, 2005). Although this approach is a well-accepted
91 common framework and has been demonstrated as a good approximation (Arellano-
92 García et al., 2015; Baltzis et al., 2001; Dorado et al., 2012, 2008; Mpanias and Baltzis,
93 1998), its expandability to industrial applications is still scarce, due to the difficulty to
94 obtain a reliable set of data.

95 This work aimed to apply a dynamic mathematical model to simulate the performance
96 of an on-site BTF treating styrene emissions under oscillating inlet concentrations and
97 operated under intermittent spraying, a common industrial protocol. The model was
98 adapted on the basis of the one proposed by San-Valero et al. (2015) for isopropanol (a
99 highly soluble compound); this model was initially created for simulating systems with
100 variable inlet concentration patterns and gas flow rates, and with cyclic conditions
101 between irrigation and non-irrigation periods. The model was calibrated with laboratory
102 data on a BTF degrading styrene for 75 days (San-Valero et al., 2017). Afterwards, the
103 model was validated by predicting the performance of almost two months of operation
104 of a pilot BTF working in a fiber-reinforced facility (Álvarez-Hornos et al., 2017). This
105 work appears as a first attempt to model the dynamic response of an industrial BTF
106 treating variable styrene emissions, thus contributing to the development of predictive
107 tools for helping practitioners to expand the application of biotrickling filtration to
108 industry.

109 **2. Materials and Methods**

110 2.1. Lab-scale BTF operation

111 The lab-scale BTF consisted of a cylindrical column (0.144 m inner diameter, 1.63 m
112 height) with a working packed volume of 20 L (working height: 1.23 m) coupled to an
113 external recirculation tank with a 6 L capacity for column irrigation. The BTF was filled

114 with polypropylene rings with a 25 mm nominal diameter and 207 m² m⁻³ surface area
 115 (a) with 92% void fraction (θ_P) (Flexiring[®], Koch-Glitsch B.V.B.A., Belgium). The
 116 liquid phase was intermittently irrigated from the recirculation tank by a centrifugal
 117 pump with a frequency of irrigation of 15 min every 2 h. The liquid flow rate was set at
 118 2.7 L min⁻¹, which is equivalent to a liquid velocity of 10 m h⁻¹. The air stream was
 119 doped with styrene using a syringe pump (New Era, NE 1000 model, USA) at
 120 concentrations of 0.18–0.32 g C m⁻³. The gas flow rate was adjusted by a mass flow
 121 controller (Bronkhorst Hi-Tec, the Netherlands) in the range of 2.4–4.8 m³ h⁻¹
 122 depending on the operation period. During the BTF operation, the inlet load (IL)
 123 increased from 22 g C m⁻³ h⁻¹ up to 43 g C m⁻³ h⁻¹ by decreasing the EBRT from 30 s to
 124 15 s. Subsequently, the EBRT was maintained at 15 s and the inlet concentration was
 125 set to obtain ILs of 13–74 g C m⁻³ h⁻¹. The selected conditions for calibration purposes
 126 are compiled in Table 1, corresponding to the average daily data representing the stable
 127 conditions of the BTF performance. The purge of 3 L of the recirculation tank was
 128 carried out once per week, and it represented less than 3% of carbon fed to the reactor
 129 during the week. Further details can be found in San-Valero et al. (2017).

130

131 Table 1. Experimental data used for the calibration of the BTF model (San-Valero et al.,

132 2017). \pm represents standard deviation

Days	IL (g C m ⁻³ h ⁻¹)	Inlet conc. (mg C m ⁻³)	EBRT (s)	EC (g C m ⁻³ h ⁻¹)
15-36	22	184	30	20.5 \pm 1.1
42-47	33	184	20	21.1 \pm 1.6
50-60	43	181	15	17.9 \pm 3.1
63-67	23	98	15	9.4 \pm 2.3
68-70	74	312	15	27.5 \pm 4.2
71-75	13	55	15	7.9 \pm 0.9

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136 2.2. On-site pilot BTF operation

137 The pilot scale BTF (VOCUS[®], Pas Solutions BV, the Netherlands) consisted of a
138 packed reactor, which has an effective volume of 0.6 m³ and is filled with a structured
139 packing material (PAS Winded Media) with a void space of 93 %, a specific surface
140 area of 410 m² m⁻³, and a recirculation tank of 0.4 m³. Part of the industrial emission
141 was fed to the BTF using a blower and a variable frequency drive. The BTF was
142 operated in a counter-current mode, the polluted air stream was blown at the bottom of
143 the column, and the recirculated water was intermittently irrigated (10 min per hour) on
144 the top at a flow rate of 2.7 m⁻³ h⁻¹. The BTF unit was operated for more than one year
145 with EBRTs varying between 31 s and 66 s. For modeling purposes, the last 52 days of
146 operation were chosen as representatives of a stable biofilm. In this period, the reactor
147 was operated at daily average ILs at 6–25 g styrene m⁻³ h⁻¹ (5–23 g C m⁻³ h⁻¹) and at a
148 constant EBRT of 31 s.

149 2.3. Model description

150 The dynamic model of this study was previously applied by San-Valero et al. (2015) for
151 isopropanol removal. The model includes two components, a pollutant (in this case,
152 styrene) and oxygen, and considers irrigation and non-irrigation periods. The model
153 considers the following well-accepted assumptions in the field:

154 (1) The gas phase flowed in a plug flow regime along the filter bed, thus neglecting
155 axial dispersion.

156 (2) The adsorption of pollutants in the packing material was negligible.

157 (3) The packing material was completely covered by a biofilm, which was
158 completely covered by the liquid phase.

159 (4) The gas–liquid interface was in equilibrium according to Henry's law.

160 (5) Biodegradation took place only in the biofilm.

161 The model equations are summarized as follows (*i* denotes styrene or oxygen):

162 Mass balance in the gas phase

163
$$\theta_G \frac{\partial C_{G_i}}{\partial t} = -v_G \frac{\partial C_{G_i}}{\partial z} - K_L a_i \left(\frac{C_{G_i}}{H_i} - C_{L_i} \right) \quad (1)$$

164 Mass balance in the liquid phase

165
$$\theta_L \frac{\partial C_{L_i}}{\partial t} = v_L \frac{\partial C_{L_i}}{\partial z} + K_L a_i \left(\frac{C_{G_i}}{H_i} - C_{L_i} \right) - \frac{D_i a}{\beta} (C_{L_i} - S_{i,1}) \quad (2)$$

166 Mass balance in the biofilm

167
$$\frac{\partial S_i}{\partial t} = f(X_v) D_i \frac{\partial^2 S_i}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\mu_{\max} X_v}{Y_i} \frac{S_{sty}}{S_{sty} + K_{sty}} \frac{S_o}{S_o + K_o} \quad (3)$$

168 During periods of irrigation, the mass balances were described as follows: styrene and
169 oxygen from the gas phase circulate through the column by considering the convective
170 transport. Styrene and oxygen are transferred to the liquid phase, with the mass flux at
171 the gas–liquid interface described by the global mass transfer coefficients (K_{L_i}). The
172 mass balance of the mobile liquid phase is produced by the circulation of the liquid
173 phase in the counter-current mode with the gas phase, which is described by the
174 convective transport equation. The liquid concentration at the top of the column is the
175 result of the mass balance in the recirculation tank considering ideal stirring during
176 irrigation and no biodegradation:

177
$$\frac{\partial C_{L_i}}{\partial t} = \frac{Q_L}{V_T} (C_{L_{i,z=0}} - C_{L_{i,z=Z}}) \quad (4)$$

178 The mass transfer from liquid to biofilm of both components is a function of the
179 specific surface area of the packing material (*a*), the diffusion coefficient in water (*D_i*),
180 and the thickness of the liquid film (*β*). In the biofilm, diffusion and biodegradation take

181 place simultaneously; the former is described by Fick's second law and the latter by a
182 Monod expression including oxygen limitation.
183 During non-irrigation periods, the liquid phase is considered a stagnant phase without
184 dynamic hold-up, so there is no convective transport ($v_L=0$), and the pollutant
185 concentration of the recirculating water remains constant. The main difference with
186 respect to San-Valero et al. (2015) is the phenomenon accounting for the mass transfer
187 from the gas phase to the stagnant liquid. It was demonstrated that in the case of high
188 water-soluble compounds, the stagnant phase serves as a pollutant sink (mass transfer
189 resistance negligible). In the case of styrene, it was assumed that the resistance of the
190 stagnant liquid is the same than that of during irrigation.

191 2.4. Numerical resolution

192 The partial differential equations were two second-order nonlinear distributed systems.
193 The method of lines (MOL) was applied to solve the systems by generating a uniform
194 grid in the spatial dimensions: the height of the reactor and the biofilm thickness. For
195 each node, the partial derivatives were replaced by finite difference approximations.
196 The optimal discretization in terms of the result and time computing was 10 sections
197 along the bed (11 nodes) and 20 sections in the biofilm (21 nodes). Increasing the
198 discretization did not produced substantial variations on the model estimation. The set
199 of differential equations was solved with the implicit integration method from
200 MATLAB[®], ode23t, which is the implementation of the trapezoidal rule using a free
201 interpolant and is especially suitable to moderately stiff systems.
202 The execution of the model was implemented in MATLAB[®] by creating a graphical
203 user interface (GUI-MATLAB[®]) to allow specifying variable gas and inlet
204 concentration patterns, as well as the duration and frequency of the spraying cycles.

205 Further details can be found elsewhere (San-Valero et al., 2016). A conceptual scheme
 206 of the model resolution is shown in Fig. 1.

207

208 Fig. 1. Conceptual scheme of the model implementation and resolution.

209 The overall gas–liquid mass transfer coefficient of styrene and the maximum growth
 210 rate were determined by the calibration of the model to the experimental data by
 211 minimizing the objective function (OF), which was defined as the sum of the norm of
 212 the deviation between the RE predicted by the model (RE_{mod}) and the experimental one
 213 (RE_{exp}):

$$214 \quad OF = \sum_{i=1}^N \left(norm \left(RE_{mod} - RE_{exp} \right) \right) \quad (5)$$

215 The parameter estimation was conducted by a MATLAB® algorithm, *fminsearch*, which
 216 consisted of searching the minimum of the unconstrained multivariable function using
 217 the simplex search method proposed by Lagarias et al. (1998). This direct search
 218 method does not use numerical or analytic gradients.

219 **3. Results**

220 **3.1 Model calibration**

221 The calibration of the dynamic model was performed with data from a styrene-
 222 degrading BTF operated at variable EBRTs and ILs (San-Valero et al., 2017). The

223 results correspond to the average data at the end of each operational condition tested
224 (Table 1) when the BTF achieved stable performance.

225 The global gas–liquid mass transfer coefficient of styrene ($K_{La_{sty}}$) and the maximum
226 growth rate (μ_{max}) were chosen as the calibration parameters. Parnian et al. (2016)
227 determined the mass transfer coefficient of styrene in an abiotic BTF packed with
228 pumice grains and steel pall rings. They found an increase in the K_{La} from 54–70 h^{-1} at
229 30°C on the countercurrent gas-to-liquid flow ratio that varied in the range of 7.5–32,
230 with a potential dependence. The variation in the gas-to-liquid flow ratio in this study
231 was in a narrow range from 16–31 and at room temperature; thus, both factors (the gas-
232 to-liquid flow ratio and temperature) seem to indicate that variations should be lower
233 than 11%. The influence of EBRT on K_{La} was considered negligible in the tested range
234 in comparison with the inherent simplicity of the model to represent the complex
235 phenomena occurring in a BTF (e.g., uneven wetted biofilm, irregular biofilm growth,
236 etc.).

237 The rest of the model parameters are shown in Table 2. The physicochemical
238 parameters were taken from the literature (Fan et al., 1990; Reid et al., 1987; Sander,
239 2005), except the overall mass-transfer coefficient for oxygen, which was estimated
240 from previous experiments (San-Valero et al., 2014). Among the kinetic parameters, the
241 yield coefficient of styrene was estimated from the CO_2 production reported by
242 Sempere et al. (2011), and the yield coefficient of oxygen was stoichiometrically
243 calculated. Half-saturation constants were taken from literature (Jung and Park, 2005;
244 Shareefdeen et al., 1993). Biofilm and liquid properties (biofilm thickness (δ), liquid
245 film thickness (β), and biofilm properties (X_v , θ_B)) were taken from our previous work,
246 in which the model was calibrated using the same experimental setup as the removal of

247 isopropanol emissions in air by BTF (San-Valero et al., 2015), except for the fraction
 248 occupied by the liquid film (θ_L), which was experimentally determined.
 249 The calibration procedure based on the minimization of the OF defined in Eq. 5 resulted
 250 in a global mass transfer coefficient of styrene of $1.14 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and a maximum growth
 251 rate of $2.65 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The value of the global mass transfer coefficient of styrene (41 h^{-1})
 252 is in agreement with the order of magnitude expected from the values of Parnian et al.
 253 (2016) considering the differences in the operational conditions. The values of the
 254 maximum growth rate of the same order of magnitude were previously reported in
 255 biofilters treating styrene (Jorio et al., 2005, 2003).

256

257

Table 2: BTF model parameters

	Specific Value	Reference
Physicochemical parameters		
$D_{\text{sty}} (\text{m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1})$	8.97×10^{-10}	(Reid et al., 1987)
$D_{\text{O}} (\text{m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1})$	2.0×10^{-9}	(Reid et al., 1987)
$f(X_v)$	0.35	(Fan et al., 1990)
H_{sty}	0.1	(Sander, 2005)
H_{O}	31.4	(Sander, 2005)
$K_{\text{LaO}} (\text{s}^{-1})$	0.013	This work
Kinetical data		
$K_{\text{O}} (\text{g m}^{-3})$	0.26	(Shareefdeen et al., 1993)
Y_{sty}	0.33	This work
Y_{O}	0.12	Stoichiometric balance
$K_{\text{sty}} (\text{g m}^{-3})$	0.154	(Jung and Park, 2005)
Biofilm and liquid film properties		
$\delta (\text{m})$	60×10^{-6}	(San-Valero et al., 2015)
$\beta (\text{m})$	3.8×10^{-6}	(San-Valero et al., 2015)
$X_v (\text{kg m}^{-3})$	50	(San-Valero et al., 2015)
θ_L	0.093	This work
θ_B	0.18	(San-Valero et al., 2015)

258

259 The good agreement between the model predictions and the experimental data in the
 260 calibration step is shown in Fig. 2, in which the relationship between the modeled and

261 the experimental EC is plotted for the three tested EBRTs (15, 20, and 30 s). The model
 262 prediction fit the experimental data with deviations below $\pm 20\%$ of the relative error.
 263 Statistical analysis was conducted and revealed a correlation between the modeled and
 264 the experimental EC with a goodness of fit of 0.84 using the normalized mean square
 265 error. The greatest deviations (23%) were obtained at the ILs of $23 \text{ g C m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ (EBRT
 266 =15 s) and $22 \text{ g C m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ (EBRT =30 s). In the first case, the modeled EC was 11.5 g C
 267 $\text{m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ versus the experimental EC at $9.4 \pm 2.3 \text{ g C m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$. Therefore, the EC predicted
 268 by the model was within the error experimentally observed. In the second case, the
 269 model underestimated the experimental value of the EC from $20.4 \pm 1.1 \text{ g C m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ to
 270 $15.7 \text{ g C m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$, as predicted by the model. Note that this deviation coincided with the
 271 start-up of the BTF, and it may be attributed to the fact that the biofilm properties in this
 272 stage could be under evolution. The RE achieved by the model (72%) is close to the
 273 other experimental data achieved with mature biofilms. For example, Pérez et al. (2015)
 274 obtained an RE of 75–80 % using the same EBRT (30 s), a similar IL ($22 \text{ g m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$), and
 275 the same irrigation frequency after more than 130 days from start-up.

276
 277 Fig. 2: Comparison between the experimental and the modeled EC of the laboratory
 278 BTF from the model calibration
 279 To evaluate whether the model could predict the variation in EC caused by the increase
 280 in the IL, simulations were performed for the conditions experimentally tested at an

281 EBRT of 15 s (Fig. 3). The model accurately predicted the variation in EC caused by
 282 the increase in the IL. At 15 s, the BTF did not achieve a complete degradation of
 283 styrene at any IL tested. However, an increase in the IL led to an increase in the EC.
 284 Thus, it seems to indicate that the mass transfer limited the system instead of the
 285 biodegradation kinetic, as the microorganisms were able to remove more styrene if it is
 286 transferred to the biofilm. In this regard, the model was able to reproduce the
 287 characteristic curve of the BTF performance and to predict the limits of the application
 288 of this technology for styrene abatement. The experimental maximum EC was 28 ± 4 g
 289 $\text{C m}^{-3} \text{h}^{-1}$, and the model predicted a maximum EC of $29 \text{ g C m}^{-3} \text{h}^{-1}$, which was within
 290 the experimental error.

291
 292 Fig. 3: Model prediction of the relationship between the EC and the IL of the laboratory
 293 BTF working at an EBRT of 15 s
 294 Aside from modeling a satisfactorily steady-state operation, the model predicted with a
 295 high level of correspondence the continuous monitoring of the gas phase styrene
 296 concentration influenced by the cycles of irrigation on a complete day of operation (Fig.
 297 4a, experiment IL = $22 \text{ g C m}^{-3} \text{h}^{-1}$, EBRT = 30 s). For a daily average outlet
 298 concentration in the gas phase lower than 50 mg C m^{-3} , the pattern emission showed
 299 small peaks of styrene (from 21 up to 35 mg C m^{-3}) matching with the irrigation
 300 periods, creating a clear dynamic pattern. The model predicted the occurrence of these

301 perturbations (peaks of pollutant during irrigation) with the same duration by
302 considering the cycling between irrigation and non-irrigation periods, which is a
303 remarkable operation parameter in industrial BTFs. In the case of a daily average outlet
304 concentration of $\sim 70 \text{ mg C m}^{-3}$, the perturbation of the spraying is not noticeable in
305 comparison with the instantaneous variations (Fig 4b, experiment $IL = 33 \text{ g C m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$,
306 $EBRT = 20 \text{ s}$). The capability of the model to reproduce a dynamic pattern on an
307 industrial scale is important to evaluate its effect, which can be optimized in the
308 function of the target pollutant. For styrene, it seems that irrigation frequency could be
309 increased or diminished in the function of the needs of operational parameters, such as
310 nutrients, pH, or pressure drop, without adversely impacting the daily averaged removal
311 efficiency.

312
313 Fig. 4: Experimental pattern and model predictions corresponding to the instantaneous
314 outlet styrene concentration of the laboratory BTF: a) $IL = 22 \text{ g C m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$, $EBRT = 30 \text{ s}$
315 b) $IL = 33 \text{ g C m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$, $EBRT = 20 \text{ s}$. Arrows denote 15 min of spraying.

316 A different behavior was observed for isopropanol under an irrigation/non-irrigation
 317 cyclic operation: a complete removal was attained during non-irrigation, while peaks of
 318 high outlet concentrations (40–50% of inlet concentrations) were observed during
 319 irrigation. The decrease in irrigation frequency from 15 min every 1.5 h to 15 min every
 320 3 h caused a decrease in the daily average outlet concentrations from 86–59 mg C Nm⁻³
 321 (San-Valero et al., 2013). The fact that both pollutants show different behavior during
 322 non-irrigation periods is noteworthy. In the treatment of isopropanol, a complete
 323 removal was attained during periods without irrigation, demonstrating that the
 324 resistance to mass transfer of the stagnant liquid phase was negligible compared with
 325 that occurring during periods with irrigation. In contrast, a similar mass transfer
 326 resistance of the mobile liquid (irrigation) and the stagnant liquid (non-irrigation)
 327 reproduces in large extent the dynamic pattern of styrene emissions. This result shows
 328 the applicability of the model to pollutants with different affinities to water.

329 3.2 Model sensitivity

330 The sensitivity of the model was evaluated comparing the relative changes in the outlet
 331 concentration by the variation of 50% of the mass transfer coefficient of styrene ($K_{La_{sty}}$),
 332 kinetic parameters (μ_{max} , K_{sty}), biofilm thickness (δ), liquid thickness (β) diffusivity of
 333 styrene (D_{sty}), and Henry law's constant of styrene (H_{sty}). The sensitivity of the model to
 334 each parameter was carried out following that proposed by Baquerizo et al. (2005):

$$335 \quad sensitivity = \frac{\frac{\Delta C_G^{out}}{C_{G_d}^{out}}}{\left| \frac{\Delta p}{p_d} \right|} \quad (6)$$

336 where C_G^{out} is the outlet concentration of the gas phase and p is the evaluated parameter.
 337 Subscript d refers to the default values. The analysis was performed using the operational

338 conditions corresponding to an IL of $22 \text{ g C m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ and an EBRT of 30 s. The results are
 339 shown in Table 3.

340 Table 3: Sensitivity analysis of the BTF model

Parameter	Δ (%)	Sensitivity, C_G^{out}
$K_{L\text{sty}}$	- 50	0.699
	+ 50	-0.226
μ_{max}	- 50	0.792
	+ 50	-0.340
K_{sty}	- 50	-0.189
	+ 50	0.113
δ	- 50	2.151
	+ 50	-0.642
β	- 50	-1.094
	+ 50	0.868
D_{sty}	- 50	0.770
	+ 50	-0.377
H_{sty}	-50	-1.175
	+ 50	0.830

341

342 As shown in Table 3, the model was sensitive to the physicochemical parameters. The
 343 most sensitive value was found for low values of biofilm thickness. The analysis also
 344 revealed that the liquid thickness, the Henry's law constant, the mass transfer
 345 coefficient of styrene, and the diffusion coefficient of styrene had a notable impact on
 346 model predictions. Regarding the kinetic parameters, the most sensitive was the
 347 maximum growth rate. This finding is consistent with that reported in previous
 348 literature. For example, Baquerizo et al. (2005) found that specific biofilm thickness and
 349 specific surface area (here lumped by β and $K_{L\text{A}}$) were the most sensitive parameters in
 350 the modeling of a biofilter for ammonia removal.

351 3.3 Model validation at on-site pilot BTF

352 The model validation was conducted using the experimental data from the pilot BTF
 353 installed in a fiber-reinforced plastic industry that treats styrene for more than one year.

354 The average daily data on the pilot BTF operated at a constant EBRT of 31 s and

355 variable ILs of $5\text{--}23\text{ g C m}^{-3}\text{ h}^{-1}$ were compiled. This set of data was recommended by
356 the authors for scale-up purposes and considered to be representative of an active and
357 stable biofilm (Álvarez-Hornos et al., 2017). In the pilot testing, the styrene
358 concentration in the inlet air fluctuated from 40 mg Nm^{-3} to 350 mg Nm^{-3} associated
359 with the fluctuations in the manufacturing processes of the factory. As an illustrative
360 example, Fig. 5 shows a typical emission on one day. However, as the average daily
361 concentration was the only data available, the inlet concentration was considered
362 constant during the day for modeling purposes. When the inlet concentration was not
363 available during one day, IL was approximated as a piecewise step between the two
364 closest times.

365
366 Fig. 5: Typical fluctuations of styrene concentrations in the air emissions treated by the
367 pilot BTF installed in a fiber-reinforced plastic industry

368 The model was applied using the parameters listed in Table 2, except for the physical
369 properties corresponding to the packing material used in this setup, which is different
370 from that used at laboratory experiments ($a=410\text{ m}^2\text{ m}^{-3}$, $\theta_P=93\%$) and the overall mass
371 transfer coefficient of oxygen ($K_{LaO}=0.0121\text{ s}^{-1}$), which was determined by the
372 correlation specifically developed for this packing as proposed in San-Valero et al.
373 (2014). Fig. 6 depicts the experimental IL and EC as the data points along with the
374 model ones (continuous line). The data obtained by the model corresponded to the

375 instantaneous variations (order of seconds), thus resulting in small oscillations in the EC
376 plots associated with the irrigation effect on the outlet emission. This transitory effect
377 could be considered negligible in terms of the average daily EC. The goodness of fit of
378 the model and the experimental data was 0.84 according to the normalized mean square
379 error. The model was able to successfully represent the on-site pilot BTF under transient
380 conditions of loading. For example, on day 23 the model predicted an EC of $\sim 15 \text{ g C m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$
381 at an IL of $\sim 18 \text{ g C m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$; on the next day the EC decreased until $\sim 5.0 \text{ g C m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$
382 at IL of $\sim 5.6 \text{ g C m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$. The simulation of the model enabled the prediction of the
383 overall performance of an industrial installation for a period over 50 days with
384 significant correspondence. The slight deviations between the model predictions and the
385 experimental data could be attributed to the fact that the simulations were conducted
386 using the average daily IL rather than the instantaneous fluctuations of the industrial
387 emission (Fig. 5).

388 The model reproduced the performance of the BTFs on both laboratory and on-site pilot
389 scales by applying the same phenomena and using the same biofilm thickness. This did
390 not occur during the treatment of hydrophilic compounds, in which experimental
391 evidence supported by model predictions confirmed an excessive and uncontrolled
392 biofilm growth on the industrial scale compared with that of the laboratory scale (San-
393 Valero et al., 2015). The results obtained in this work seem to indicate that the removal
394 of industrial emissions of moderately hydrophobic compounds, such as styrene, by
395 BTFs could be characterized by slow biofilm growth. Previous authors have observed
396 that styrene abatement at industrial sites could lead to difficulties in establishing a stable
397 biofilm in the short term in industrial installation (Álvarez-Hornos et al., 2017; Webster
398 et al., 1999). However, when stable biofilm is established, slow biofilm growth could
399 benefit the long-term performance of the industrial unit, achieving an RE similar to that

400 of the laboratory unit, and minimizing other operational problems, such as clogging or
401 pollutant accumulation within the biofilm.

402

403 Fig. 6: Experimental evolution of the on-site BTF installed in a fiber-reinforced plastic
404 industry along with the model simulations: a) IL; b) EC.

405 The approach considered in the development of this model, which was fitted by the
406 calibration of only two parameters, $K_{L\text{asty}}$ and μ_{max} , was valid to represent the
407 phenomena occurring in the treatment of styrene by BTFs in the laboratory and at
408 industrial scale, and in steady and dynamic conditions, improving the knowledge about
409 the rate-limiting step of the process. From a practical point of view, this approach can
410 be used by practitioners in the design and operation of industrial BTFs treating styrene
411 and other pollutants by adapting the related parameters. The developed model herein is
412 the base to predict and evaluate styrene abatement under new and promising bioreactor
413 configurations, such as a two-phase partitioning bioreactor, which is potentially
414 interesting for low-soluble compounds such as styrene (see part 2).

415

416

417 **4. Conclusions**

418 A dynamic model to simulate a styrene-degrading laboratory BTF was developed
419 through a set of differential equations switching from irrigation to non-irrigation periods
420 by implementing in a graphical user interface (GUI-MATLAB®). The results obtained
421 herein with those results previously on modeling the isopropanol emissions under cyclic
422 irrigation/non-irrigation periods are of interest to show that the rate-limiting step of the
423 process depends on the water solubility of the compound. The daily average elimination
424 capacity of a pilot BTF installed in a fiber-reinforced plastic industry working under
425 oscillating inlet concentrations and loading was successfully simulated, thus showing
426 the robustness of the model as a predictive tool.

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431 **References**

- 432 Alonso, C., Suidan, M.T., Kim, B.R., Kim, B.J., 1998. Dynamic mathematical model
433 for the biodegradation of VOCs in a biofilter: biomass accumulation study.
434 Environ. Sci. Technol. 32, 3118–3123. doi:10.1021/es9711021
- 435 Álvarez-Hornos, F.J., Gabaldón, C., Martínez-Soria, V., Marzal, P., Peña-roja, J.-M.,
436 2009. Mathematical modeling of the biofiltration of ethyl acetate and toluene and
437 their mixture. Biochem. Eng. J. 43, 169–177. doi:10.1016/j.bej.2008.09.014
- 438 Álvarez-Hornos, F.J., Martínez-Soria, V., Marzal, P., Izquierdo, M., Gabaldón, C.,
439 2017. Performance and feasibility of biotrickling filtration in the control of styrene

440 industrial air emissions. *Int. Biodeterior. Biodegradation* 119, 329–335.
441 doi:10.1016/j.ibiod.2016.10.016

442 Arellano-García, L., Dorado, A.D., Morales-Guadarrama, A., Sacristan, E., Gamisans,
443 X., Revah, S., 2015. Modeling the effects of biomass accumulation on the
444 performance of a biotrickling filter packed with PUF support for the alkaline
445 biotreatment of dimethyl disulfide vapors in air. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 99,
446 97–107. doi:10.1007/s00253-014-5929-7

447 Baltzis, B.C., Mpanias, C.J., Bhattacharya, S., 2001. Modeling the removal of VOC
448 mixtures in biotrickling filters. *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* 72, 389–401.
449 doi:10.1002/1097-0290(20000220)72:4<389::AID-BIT1001>3.0.CO;2-#

450 Baquerizo, G., Maestre, J.P., Sakuma, T., Deshusses, M.A., Gamisans, X., Gabriel, D.,
451 Lafuente, J., 2005. A detailed-model of a biofilter for ammonia removal: Model
452 parameters analysis and model validation. *Chem. Eng. J.* 113, 205–214.
453 doi:10.1016/j.cej.2005.03.003

454 Das, C., Chowdhury, R., Bhattacharya, P., 2011. Experiments and three phase
455 modelling of a biofilter for the removal of toluene and trichloroethylene.
456 *Bioprocess Biosyst. Eng.* 34, 447–458. doi:10.1007/s00449-010-0487-6

457 Derwent, R.G., Jenkin, M.E., Saunders, S.M., Pilling, M.J., 1998. Photochemical ozone
458 creation potentials for organic compounds in northwest Europe calculated with a
459 master chemical mechanism. *Atmos. Environ.* 32, 2429–2441. doi:10.1016/S1352-
460 2310(98)00053-3

461 Deshusses, M.A., Webster, T.S., 2000. Construction and Economics of a Pilot/Full-
462 Scale Biological Trickling Filter Reactor for the Removal of Volatile Organic
463 Compounds from Polluted Air. *J. Air Waste Manage. Assoc.* 50, 1947–1956.
464 doi:10.1080/10473289.2000.10464220

465 Devinny, J.S., Ramesh, J., 2005. A phenomenological review of biofilter models.
466 Chem. Eng. J. 113, 187–196. doi:10.1016/j.cej.2005.03.005

467 Dorado, A.D., Baquerizo, G., Maestre, J.P., Gamisans, X., Gabriel, D., Lafuente, J.,
468 2008. Modeling of a bacterial and fungal biofilter applied to toluene abatement:
469 Kinetic parameters estimation and model validation. Chem. Eng. J. 140, 52–61.
470 doi:10.1016/j.cej.2007.09.004

471 Dorado, A.D., Lafuente, J., Gabriel, D., Gamisans, X., 2012. Biomass accumulation in a
472 biofilter treating toluene at high loads - Part 2: Model development, calibration and
473 validation. Chem. Eng. J. 209, 670–676. doi:10.1016/j.cej.2012.08.019

474 European Union, 2010. Directive 2010/75/EU of the European Parliament and of the
475 council of 24 November 2010 on industrial emissions (integrated pollution
476 prevention and control) (Recast), Official Journal of the European Union.

477 Fan, L.-S., Leyva-Ramos, R., Wisecarver, K.D., Zehner, B.J., 1990. Diffusion of phenol
478 through a biofilm grown on activated carbon particles in a draft-tube three-phase
479 fluidized-bed bioreactor. Biotechnol. Bioeng. 35, 279–286.
480 doi:10.1002/bit.260350309

481 Jorio, H., Brzezinski, R., Heitz, M., 2005. A novel procedure for the measurement of
482 the kinetics of styrene biodegradation in a biofilter. J. Chem. Technol. Biotechnol.
483 80, 796–804. doi:10.1002/jctb.1245

484 Jorio, H., Payre, G., Heitz, M., 2003. Mathematical modeling of gas-phase biofilter
485 performance. J. Chem. Technol. Biotechnol. 78, 834–846. doi:10.1002/jctb.835

486 Jung, I.G., Park, C.H., 2005. Characteristics of styrene degradation by *Rhodococcus*
487 *pyridinovorans* isolated from a biofilter. Chemosphere 61, 451–456.
488 doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2005.03.007

489 Kim, S., Deshusses, M.A., 2003. Development and experimental validation of a

490 conceptual model for biotrickling filtration of H₂S. *Environ. Prog.* 22, 119–128.
491 doi:10.1002/ep.670220214

492 Lafita, C., Peña-Roja, J.-M., Gabaldón, C., Martínez-Soria, V., 2012. Full-scale
493 biotrickling filtration of volatile organic compounds from air emission in wood-
494 coating activities. *J. Chem. Technol. Biotechnol.* 87, 732–738.
495 doi:10.1002/jctb.3716

496 Lagarias, J.C., Reeds, J.A., Wright, M.H., Wright, P.E., 1998. Convergence Properties
497 of the Nelder-Mead Simplex Method in Low Dimensions. *SIAM J. Optim.* 9, 112–
498 147.

499 Liao, Q., Tian, X., Chen, R., Zhu, X., 2008. Mathematical model for gas-liquid two-
500 phase flow and biodegradation of a low concentration volatile organic compound
501 (VOC) in a trickling biofilter. *Int. J. Heat Mass Transf.* 51, 1780–1792.
502 doi:10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2007.07.007

503 Lim, J.S., Hwang, J.W., Choi, C.Y., Kim, B.H., Park, S., 2005. A pilot-scale rotating
504 drum biotrickling filter for removing gaseous styrene. *Key Eng. Mater.* 277–279,
505 517–522. doi:10.4028/www.scientific.net/KEM.277-279.517

506 Lu, C., 2001. Removal of styrene vapor from waste gases by a trickle-bed air biofilter.
507 *J. Hazard. Mater.* 82, 233–245. doi:10.1016/S0304-3894(00)00347-2

508 Mpanias, C.J., Baltzis, B.C., 1998. An experimental and modeling study on the removal
509 of mono-chlorobenzene vapor in biotrickling filters. *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* 59, 328–
510 43. doi:10.1002/(SICI)1097-0290(19980805)59:3<328::AID-BIT9>3.0.CO;2-D

511 National Toxicology Program (NTP), 2016. Report on Carcinogens, Fourteenth Edition.

512 Okkerse, W.J.H., Ottengraf, S.P.P., Osinga-Kuipers, B., Okkerse, M., 1999. Biomass
513 accumulation and clogging in biotrickling filters for waste gas treatment.
514 Evaluation of a dynamic model using dichloromethane as a model pollutant.

515 Biotechnol. Bioeng. 63, 418–430. doi:10.1002/(SICI)1097-
516 0290(19990520)63:4<418::AID-BIT5>3.0.CO;2-0

517 Parnian, P., Zamir, S.M., Shojaosadati, S.A., 2016. Effect of operating temperature on
518 styrene mass transfer characteristics in a biotrickling filter. Environ. Technol. 284,
519 926–933. doi:10.1080/09593330.2016.1226960

520 Pérez, M.C., Álvarez-Hornos, F.J., Portune, K., Gabaldón, C., 2015. Abatement of
521 styrene waste gas emission by biofilter and biotrickling filter: comparison of
522 packing materials and inoculation procedures. Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol. 99,
523 19–32. doi:10.1007/s00253-014-5773-9

524 Reid, R.C., Prausnitz, J.M., Poling, B.E., 1987. The properties of gases and liquids.
525 McGraw-Hill Book Company, New York, EEUU.

526 San-Valero, P., Alcántara, S., Peña-Roja, J.M., Álvarez-Hornos, F.J., Gabaldón, C.,
527 2016. A Tool for Predicting the Dynamic Response of Biotrickling Filters for VOC
528 Removal. Chem. Eng. Commun. 203, 476–487.
529 doi:10.1080/00986445.2015.1025954

530 San-Valero, P., Gabaldón, C., Peña-roja, J.M., Quijano, G., 2017. Enhanced styrene
531 removal in a two-phase partitioning bioreactor operated as a biotrickling filter:
532 Towards full-scale applications. Chem. Eng. J. 309, 588–595.
533 doi:10.1016/j.cej.2016.10.054

534 San-Valero, P., Peña-Roja, J.M., Álvarez-Hornos, F.J., Gabaldón, C., 2014. Modelling
535 mass transfer properties in a biotrickling filter for the removal of isopropanol.
536 Chem. Eng. Sci. 108, 47–56. doi:10.1016/j.ces.2013.12.033

537 San-Valero, P., Peña-Roja, J.M., Álvarez-Hornos, F.J., Marzal, P., Gabaldón, C., 2015.
538 Dynamic mathematical modelling of the removal of hydrophilic VOCs by
539 biotrickling filters. Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health 12, 746–766.

540 doi:10.3390/ijerph120100746

541 San-Valero, P., Peña-Roja, J.M., Sempere, F., Gabaldon, C., 2013. Biotrickling
542 filtration of isopropanol under intermittent loading conditions. *Bioprocess Biosyst.*
543 *Eng.* 36, 975–984. doi:10.1007/s00449-012-0833-y

544 Sander, R., 2005. Henry's law constants in NIST chemistry WebBook, NIST standard
545 referencedatabase number 69, in: Linstrom, P.J., Mallard, W.G. (Eds.), National
546 Institute of Standards and Technology. Gaithersburg MD 208999, USA.

547 Sempere, F., Gabaldón, C., Martínez-Soria, V., Marzal, P., Peña-roja, J.M., Alvarez-
548 Hornos, F.J., 2008. Performance evaluation of a biotrickling filter treating a
549 mixture of oxygenated VOCs during intermittent loading. *Chemosphere* 73, 1533–
550 1539. doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2008.08.037

551 Sempere, F., Martínez-Soria, V., Palau, J., Peña-Roja, J.-M., San-Valero, P.,
552 Gabaldón, C., 2011. Effects of nitrogen source and empty bed residence time on
553 the removal of styrene gaseous emissions by biotrickling filtration. *Bioprocess*
554 *Biosyst. Eng.* 34, 859–67. doi:10.1007/s00449-011-0536-9

555 Shareefdeen, Z., Baltzis, B.C., Oh, Y.-S., Bartha, R., 1993. Biofiltration of methanol
556 vapor. *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* 41, 512–524. doi:10.1002/bit.260410503

557 Webster, T.S., Cox, H.H.J., Deshusses, M.A., 1999. Resolving operational and
558 performance problems encountered in the use of a pilot/full-scale biotrickling filter
559 reactor. *Environ. Prog.* 18, 162–172. doi:10.1002/ep.670180312

560 Zarook, S.M., Shaikh, A.A., Ansar, Z., Baltzis, B.C., 1997. Biofiltration of volatile
561 organic compound (VOC) mixtures under transient conditions. *Chem. Eng. Sci.*
562 52, 4135–4142. doi:10.1016/S0009-2509(97)00256-X

563

564

565 **Nomenclature**

a	Specific surface area of the packing material
C	Concentration
D	Diffusion coefficient
f(X_v)	Correction factor of diffusivity in the biofilm according to Fan's equation
H	Henry's law constant
K	Half saturation rate constant of the substrate
K_La	Overall mass transfer coefficient of the substrate
Q	Flow rate
p	Parameter
S	Concentration in the biofilm
t	Time
v	Superficial velocity
V	Volume
x	Coordinate for the depth in the biofilm
X_v	Biomass concentration in the biofilm
Y	Yield coefficient
z	Axial coordinate in the reactor from inlet to outlet
Greek letters	
β	Thickness of the liquid film
δ	Thickness of the biofilm
θ_B	Volume fraction occupied by the biofilm
θ_G	Porosity of the bioreactor
θ_L	Volume fraction occupied by the liquid film
θ_P	Void space of the packing material
μ_{max}	Maximum specific growth rate of the substrate
Subscripts	
i	Substance (styrene and oxygen)
d	Default
G	Gas
L	Liquid
B	Biofilm
Sty	Styrene
O	Oxygen
T	Tank
Z	Height of the reactor
Superscripts	
out	outlet

566

567